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A Body Without Organs: Neoliberal Desires, Postfeminist Ideations, and Ideological Schizophrenia in *Conversations with Friends*

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Abstract:

Sally Rooney's primary concerns are Marxist critiques of neoliberal values related to private property and wealth acquisition in a purely capitalist economy. However, her bourgeois novel form has been contended for perpetuating a postfeminist purview of feminine sensibilities. The research marks a stark departure from these evaluations and establishes that Rooney's women are self-conscious and constantly pitted against an elaborate structure of kyriarchy. The protagonist of her novel, Frances, becomes the mouthpiece of ideological disillusionment and liminality by existing in a space of constantly 'becoming'. These illustrations have been substantiated by drawing on the theoretical precepts of Gilles Deleuze and Félix Guattari, which promulgate that 'ideological schizophrenia' is the only way to transcend the panopticons of the concentric circles of false consciousness permeating the sociocultural milieu of a society. They revert to primal desiring-machines and an affective 'Body without Organs' that subverts any form of structural configurations within its loci.

Keywords: Neoliberal, Postfeminist, Desiring Machines, Body without Organs, Ideological Schizophrenia.

Examining the Subversion of Neoliberalism and Postfeminism in Rooney's Novel

Rooney's Marxist Resistance Literature:

Sally Rooney's keen insight into the convoluted and paradoxical ideologies persisting within the sociocultural Superstructure of the contemporary recessionary and mechanised Ireland systematically renders its economic Base into a semiotic system of hegemonic signs – in a constant Brownian motion – colliding and quietly colluding with one another to preserve the dominant ideology of neo-capitalist affluence and material conditions in place. Rooney identifies these convoluted threads, undergoing a disjunctive fragmentation, revolving from epistemologically and philosophically cogent cultural criticisms, to the quasi-translations of a post-industrial, mechanised, and cybernetic economic system. Her complex female characters push against this Brownian motion of internalised hegemony and the covertly obfuscated significations of oppression dwelling within the economic Base by utilising the very tools of their enslavement and thereby, readily transcend them. In one such exemplary incident, Bobby in *Conversations with Friends* comments upon the efficacy of non-monogamous relationships in a contemporary neo-capitalist economy:

She said that monogamy was based on a commitment model, which served the needs of men in patrilineal societies by allowing them to pass property to their genetic offspring, traditionally facilitated by sexual entitlement to a wife. Non-monogamy could be based on an alternative model completely, Bobby said. Something more like spontaneous consent (Rooney 252).

Bobby's comment upon the alternatives of an otherwise stringent patriarchal system of private ownership and wealth hoarding encapsulates Rooney's subversion of the convoluted threads of the contemporary dominant ideology of a post-industrial, mechanised Superstructure. By marking a clear departure from the conformist and duly postfeminist 'choices' of adhering to the conventions of the predominant false consciousnesses pervading the economic Base,

Rooney constructs complex female characters that identify themselves with a polymorphous signification, which readily denounces the binaries of the mechanised Superstructure tincturing the sociocultural tapestry of a post-Celtic Tiger Ireland. Nevertheless, what is it that keeps the material conditions of an essentially impalpable ideology functional? Marxism extensively highlights the class-based bifurcations of the affluent and oppressive bourgeoisie, persisting alongside the exploited and alienated labour of the proletariat. These class distinctions, as previously discussed, formulate the Superstructure and the Base of the economy, respectively, being constantly acted upon by the Hegelian dialectics of historical materialism in tandem. In Marxist criticism, ideology is explicitly defined as the oppressed classes' belief “that the order of inequality in society is ‘natural’ or ‘pre-ordained’ and [how they] do not recognise that they are oppressed. This ... helps naturalise economic inequality and oppression” (Nayar 130). Marxism theorises about the presence of an oppressive, indoctrinated system of signs which keeps the economic Base constantly tied to the shackles of its own undoing; According to Marxist precepts, all forms of art coexist within the ideological system of signification as ‘cultural products’ which seek to reduplicate, reassert, and reify the dominant oppressive ideology contained within the mechanised Superstructure. The Marxist critique analyses how the dominant ideology pervades every cultural product that gets manufactured by the economic Base; these cultural products embody a conglomeration of the precepts of the dominant ideology that readily implement the authority of the Superstructure upon the socio-economic tapestry of the proletariat. The consumption, production, and contestation of the meaning-making processes, which are attributed to the signification of all art forms, determine how the dominant ideology is indoctrinated and impressed upon the psyche of the economic Base, as a de facto precondition of existence. All forms of art, dished out as a cultural product that ultimately proselytises and serves the covertly oppressive agendas of the mechanised Superstructure, cements this mandate in situ that art and literature can only operate within the

confines of the dominant ideology, and thus acts as the vanguards of the bourgeois sentiments: reifying and justifying the oppressive models of hierarchy, class oppression, fiscal inequalities, and an essentially overworked proletariat – preserving the affluence of the bourgeois intact. As Nayar explicates in his assessment of culture, ideology, and hegemonic structures of signification embedded within the Superstructure:

Cultural ‘products’ like films ... are created and consumed in particular contexts... such products explain the world to us. With their ‘social referents’, they help us make sense of the world, even as the world we live in helps us generate the meanings from a text. This means, works of art function as codes for experiences and realities. We ‘decode’ a work of art depending upon the contexts we occupy (Nayar 128).

The phenomenon and task assigned to a Marxist critic and thinker is “to see how such representations reflect or refract existing economic conditions so that the dominant classes retain their power in any society” (Nayar 129). The ‘sociology of consumption’ or the ‘sociology of culture’ becomes the watchword of any touchstone Marxist analysis. The cultural products are envisioned as operating within and for the benefit of the Superstructure, which manipulates and keeps in check any and every ground of subversion, thwarting the balance between the dialectics of materiality, not to provoke a socialist revolution amidst the unsuspecting proletariat. The presumed order of the day is glorified, repackaged, and resold to the economic Base, which readily preconfigures the notions of their oppressed state of existence; an existence that has been diachronically reasserted in a myriad ways seeps into the ontological condition of the proletariat’s sociology, so much so that they can ill configure an existence belying the locus of control drawn and charted out by the Superstructure. “Cultural artefacts represent the world to us ... in certain ways so that we obtain particular meanings from them” (Nayar 129), the meanings that are obtained from the cultural products sold to the

proletariat by and by, reinforce its oppressed state of existence, thus disabling any independent and subversive modulations in the ontology of the oppressed. “The sociology of culture in Marxism focuses on the social contexts of the author and the reader, the production and consumption of cultural artifacts” (Nayar 128), that is, Marxists identify and evaluate the author’s socioeconomic, cultural, and political contexts; including but not limited to their technological, funding, class, media, and race. Simultaneously, they place the reader in their consumptive context and analyse how cultural ideologies prevalent in the Superstructure determine and generate certain specific kinds and rubrics of meaning.

Broadly enumerated, “ideology enables the dominant classes to reinforce their power over the oppressed and marginalised classes because ideology serves as a system of beliefs that naturalises the unequal power relations ... as self-evident and therefore beyond questioning” (Nayar 131). The contention that arises with touchstone Marxist analysis is the unrecognized quandary of several ‘resistance literatures’; the hegemony of the Superstructure dominates language, culture, and sociology, but the presence of several subversive and renegade narratives emerging as budding offshoots from the corpus of the economy’s literary body defies the stringent Marxist lens of identifying every art form as a byproduct of the culture, as an artefact proselytizing and upholding the ideological biases of the conveniently lopsided Superstructure. Rooney’s novel would have undoubtedly become another cultural artefact analysed and discarded under the vertices of a purely socioeconomic Marxist analysis; however, she expertly utilises the tools and vehicles of the bourgeois sentiments and turns them outwards. The economic Base in Rooney’s contemporary fiction is hyperaware about its oppositions in the kyriarchal order and is perpetually self-referential about its own internalised oppressive structures. A textbook Marxist analysis of Rooney’s narrativity would render the complex collusions of the constantly counterpointing ideological dialectics moot. As Nayar has observed, “Resistance literature in every culture – working class poetry, anti-colonial writings,

or women’s narratives – has provided ideologies different from the acceptable ones” (Nayar 133); this readily establishes that the economic Base is not unthinking machinery beyond redemption, and the cultural products can be widely distinguished from the subversive texts arising from the domains of resistance literatures. Louis Althusser, a predominant thinker in the realm of Marxist evaluations, has identified this shortcoming in the touchstone Marxist critiques: “in order to remedy this traditional Marxist view that all art is ideological, the French thinker Louis Althusser proposed a new scheme” (Nayar 133). Althusser believed that all art forms have a specific relationship with the dominant ideologies of the Superstructure:

If ideology is imaginary ... and art is also about imaginary things, then there is a more complicated relationship that exists between the two. Althusser argued that art does not exist within ideology but distances itself from it ... Althusser argued that ideology is circulated through particular structures in society. These he termed Ideological State Apparatuses (Nayar 134).

Althusser foraged the herculean task of establishing the materiality of an otherwise impalpable, ideological consciousness pervading the proletariat; he explicates that ideology’s existence is materially determined in the sense that the ISAs or the Ideological State Apparatuses embody “a certain number of realities which represent themselves to the immediate observer in the form of distinct and specialized institutions” (Althusser 53). The precepts of the dominant oppressive ideology do not levitate immaterially, rather they are contained within the vessels of both ideological and repressive state apparatuses – that seek to coercively and consensually imply the principal ideations contained within their strictures respectively – Althusser determines how the ISAs and the RSAs work in tandem with one another and predominantly embody as well as deploy the hierarchical stratifications of the Superstructure. “Ideological state apparatuses include institutions and structures such as the family, religion, the media, the education system ... convince people of the ‘correctness’ of ideology by presenting it as a

desirable object or idea” (Nayar 134). The Ideological State Apparatuses ensure that the community forged by the proletariat consists of the seeds implanted by the Superstructure so that it germinates the buds of neo-capitalist sensibilities. “This is the ‘consent’ mode (as opposed to the coercive mode) of ideology dissemination” (Nayar 134). The Superstructure works on multiple levels: it not only forges the epicentre of the locus of the ideations of the false consciousnesses contained within it, but also ensures that the dissemination of these false consciousnesses coincide in manifold ways; the Ideological State Apparatuses dictate the surroundings of an individual, the sociological milieu he is born and indoctrinated in, it is the ‘private sphere’ of the individual that gyrates around the ideological biases laid onto it by the mechanised Superstructure. In contrast, the Repressive State Apparatuses or the ‘public domain’ of the individual defines and contains “the Government, the Administration, the Army, the Police, the Courts, the Prisons &c. ... the State Apparatus in question functions by violence – at least ultimately (since repression e.g. administrative repression, may take non-physical forms” (Althusser 53). This entails that “the ideology is imposed by offering a threat of violence: this is coercion of the people to accept a particular ideology” (Nayar 134). Althusser’s assertion concretises the existence of the mechanised ideology of the Superstructure, which is otherwise so deeply entrenched and engraved in the lives of the proletariat that they remain largely unaware of their functions and vehicles. “The most significant feature of ideology is that it is invisible. This means we are not aware of ideology because it pervades our lives – ideology is a lived reality where the features have become so familiar as to be invisible” (Nayar 135); by dictating and bifurcating the segments of the ‘private’ as well as the ‘public’ domain that enshrouds an individual’s life, Althusser exposes the coercive and collusive functioning of ideology as a de facto reality of our lives: his analysis also vindicates the presence of resistance literatures like that of Rooney’s Marxist outlook and neoliberalist critiques, for both the Ideological and Repressive State Apparatuses become a vessel containing the material

existence of ideology, which makes art not merely the compounded product of culture but an extrication from it. “By circulating images of the happy heterosexual family these media representations suggest that only a heterosexual family is a real family” (Nayar 134), the dominant and mainstream depictions of conventional ideological symbols are a direct adversary of the cause of the proletariat – the media, religion, and schools constantly reinforcing an image and imbuing them upon the ontology of the socioeconomic tapestry is not art – it is the direct expression of the obfuscated program of the dominant classes. Resistance literature, like that of Rooney’s, functions outside the bounds of the material ideological vessels; the literature voicing the cause of the proletariat and expressing self-referential diatribes against the dominant mode of governance automatically assumes a position of overt subversion against the material preconditions and apparatuses of ideology. “Ideology is material because it is embedded in and works through material institutions such as the family or the schooling system ... individual[s] accept reality, understand it, and live within it. Ideology ... is hence a material reality” (Nayar 134); resistance literatures become an inward-looking glass that stands in contradiction, or rather, facing against the material apparatuses of ideological conceptions. Marxism distinguishes between the public and the private domain but strictly adheres to the binaries of the master-slave dialectic; there is little to no wriggling room for the presence of literary discourses and narrativity that mark a clear and concise departure from the vicissitudes of the ontological and material realities of the master (Superstructure, favouring the bourgeois sensibilities being reinforced vis a vis the tools of coercion and ‘manufactured consent’, as carried out by the RSAs and the ISAs respectively) and the slave (economic Base, or the proletariat being indoctrinated into a material and communal alienation of their labour and surplus value). The liminal space persisting between the binaries of the public and private domains gives rise to the subversive outtakes of resistance literature. The distinction between the public and private spheres is in direct correspondence with the

distinction between the myriad signs in Brownian motion around the binding force of the transcendental signified, wherein the State and the Superstructure act as the eternally static force, ideologically pre-ordained, to provide and posit meanings of existence for the signs arbitrarily colliding against one another. Althusser has enumerated this distinction as “the distinction between the public and the private is a distinction internal to bourgeois Law ... the domain of the State escapes it because the latter is above the Law ... it is the precondition for any distinction between public and private” (Althusser 54); the State and its sociocultural, mechanised Superstructure thus act as the transcendental signified necessary for the phenomenon of the meaning-making process. The meanings assigned to the signs never make the proletariat aware of the ‘part’ or the ‘role’ which they are playing in the grandiose metanarrative of the Superstructure, “this construction of subjects through ideology is what Althusser termed interpellation” (Nayar 135). Ideology interpellates individuals; that is, the individual subjectivity of the isolated sign in arbitrary motion is streamlined, imbued, and attributed with meaning to turn it into an ‘ideological Subject’ that adheres to the predominant principles of the Superstructure. The interpellation of identity is a double-edged sword: “interpellation is the process of consenting to ideology, accepting it, and not being aware of it ... ideology interpellates the individual as a subject but makes him/her believe s/he is a free agent” (Nayar 135). The consenting to and being aware of the predominant ideology is a psychological process, much similar to Lacan’s ‘moment of Symbolic’ wherein the infant traverses through the uncharted and primal realms of the Imaginary, and the Mirror Stage; after realizing and imitating his apparent position in the world around him, he enters the Symbolic stage, or the stage of acculturation and language acquisition; the language is the bedrock of the dominant ideologies and its promulgations. Therefore, the psychological signs of the infant’s mind seek a streamlined, ontological refuge in the ‘role’ assigned to him via the moment of

Symbolic and his interpellation into an ideological Subject. Interpellation can be seen primarily playing out in two distinct stages:

Ideology precedes the individual and an individual is inserted into the ideological scheme. There is a pre-determined set of roles out of which the individual ‘automatically’ chooses a few, all the while assuming that s/he has freely chosen them (Nayar 135).

Thus, the process of being interpellated into the realm of ideology is as psychological as it is political. Althusser’s Marxist analysis of art and its relationship with the predominant cultural precepts accounts for the fact that art, indeed, ‘distances’ itself from the sociocultural oppressive statures of the Superstructure; Rooney penned down her Marxist critique not as a cultural byproduct of the very tools that she sought to denounce, but her self-referential diatribe against the neoliberal and postfeminist realms of desire and hegemonic internalisations makes her work an adequate criticism of the convoluted contemporary culture that Ireland exists in the throes of, and what circumscribes it as an all-encompassing condition of existence.

Rooney’s Characters as Sites of Deterritorialization:

Jimenez cogitates upon the quandary of whether ‘the bourgeois romance’ plot is an adequate tool for subverting the double entanglement of neoliberal and postfeminist structures; it has duly been drawn out how Rooney’s resistance literature exists outside the bonds of ideology, but how does it do that? Where do we place Rooney’s characters as emblems of hyperaware ideological resisters, who denounce the interiority of ideology, both in their subjectivities and in their extrinsic approach to socioeconomic objectivities? Gilles Deleuze and Félix Guattari forged an extensive Marxist understanding of the contemporary crisscrossing axioms of the capital and psychological economy – that is the interlinking between the Lacanian moment of Symbolic and the acquisition of ideology, to the political

manifestations of the precepts of these neoliberal desires, instigated by the bourgeois ideology, and how they overrule the body politic's labour and hones its surplus value for capitalist production). Their groundbreaking analysis and amalgamation of Marxist critiques of the economy and Freudian psychoanalysis are extensively expounded upon in their book, *Anti-Oedipus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia*. "It would be an error to view *Anti-Oedipus* as yet another attempt at a Freud/Marx synthesis. For such an attempt always treats political economy (the flows of capital and interest) and the economy of the libido (the flow of desire as two separate economies)" (Seem xviii); but what accounts for the synthesis of libidinal desire and capitalist cash flows? Deleuze and Guattari draw on multiple authors and their philosophical analysis; unlike the latter assortment of philosophers, stuck to their revolutionary points of disposition, Deleuze and Guattari offer a point of transcendence – a point of departure from the cure itself – the subversive 'cures' become too highly invested in their streams of cognitive enunciation, they become a system of signification that bind their selves within the periphery of their approach and theology. Deleuze and Guattari explicate this phenomenon as the presence of a panoply of ideologically entrenched, concentric circles mapping the stratosphere of the proletariat's socioeconomic and ontological conditions. These circles of ideology and ontology range from the body, the mental/oedipal image, social, political, as well as the spheres of the world-historical; The Marxist and Freudian analysis base themselves within the circles of these ideological hemispheres – no critique of neo-capitalist ideology goes beyond its circle of ideological condemnation – Deleuze and Guattari seek to remedy these pitfalls of theoretical subversions and incorporate them in a novel politics based on desire and social production; one that holds Marxism accountable for its limited criticism of the realm of the socioeconomic and political, and Freudian or Lacanian psychoanalysis for their 'ambiguity' around the objectivities of myth and tragedies in their filial analysis of the father-mother binary duo

(Plastic Pills)¹. Deleuze and Guattari identify how throughout history ‘desire’ has functioned as the chief proponent of both the psychoanalytic as well the socioeconomic reality; they refer to this phenomenon as the proliferation of the ‘desiring-machines’, that is, throughout a diachronic understanding of the world/historical, the ‘desiring-machines’ have produced primitive as well as tyrannical economies; both of which were ‘territorialized’ with static emblems and ‘objectives’ of undeviating modalities. The primitive desiring-machines were based on a flow of kinship, ritual, and social inscriptions – the subjective desire was streamlined and encoded with static flows of signification, via totems and taboos. The bodies of the desiring-machines are inscribed and streamlined to determine flows, honed to curate a territorialized economy of objective production and desire. The ‘despot’ acts as “a paranoiac who has discovered the signifier” (Gilles Deleuze, *Anti-Oedipus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia* 194). He acts as an imperialist encoding desire into a centralized production, as a transcendental law-giver, a signifier supreme. Deleuze and Guattari analyse how desire and economic flows have been interlinked, synthesized, and honed in a cohesive flow to determine the socioeconomic bent of the ‘desiring-machine’ and its production. The outset of capitalism disrupts and ruptures the primitive and despotic socioeconomic encoding of desire, memory, and production; capitalism alters the site of the body of the desiring-machine to yield it unto arbitrary ‘axiomatic-flows’; mathematically and ordinally evaluated, the socioeconomic flow of desire is based on an inherent ‘deterritorialized’ production. “Capitalism is the only social machine that is constructed on the basis of decoded flows” (Gilles Deleuze, *Anti-Oedipus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia* 153). In the socioeconomic realm of capitalism, the flows are readily broken down and decoded, and desire is in flux, undergoing a perpetual desecration. There is no monarch, no despot, no primal territorialization of the desiring-machine being

¹ Plastic Pills is an electronic repository of video essays or documentaries orbiting continental philosophy, critical theory, art, politics, and postmodernism.

encoded with flows; rather, the fluctuating and axiomatic modules of cash circulation, profit, and deterritorialized productions become the watchwords of the economy. The point of rupture in the desiring-machine and its streamlined flows into mathematically arbitrary axioms of capital brings about a desertion of the ‘territories of desire’; there is an abandonment. This point of abandonment is analysed in terms of reallocated forms of wealth in Marxist praxis. An axiomatic desiring-machine ceases to be encoded with streamlined modes of kinship, memory, and an imperialist lawmaker; the production and generation of wealth is realised and coalesced into the accumulation of ‘private property’ as the socioeconomic condition moves outward from subjective desires to objectivities of axioms; the deterritorialized private property is analogous to Freud’s psychoanalytic assertion of desire. In psychoanalysis, the body and the mind have streamlined modes of libidinal assertion; devoid of external objectivities, the libidinal body does not choose its goals and remains a site of general subjective activity. The libidinal body is signified and encoded in the filial bonds of the Oedipus. The Oedipus is perennial, the unconscious subjective libidinal flow, deterritorialized in its abandonment, is seen as a site of binary bifurcation by the Oedipal, the filial tie – a tie that immediately reintroduces the deterritorialized libido unto the realms of the axiomatic desiring-machine; the simultaneous rupture, the concurrent deterritorialization is immediately reconfigured in Marxism. For Marx, the deterritorialized labour is promptly ‘reterritorialized’ vis-à-vis the re-alienation of the surplus labour from its desiring-machine. Capitalist machines thrive on decoding desires by turning them into axiomatic flows and immediately re-territorialize them with the double alienation of their subjective productivity; “the deterritorialization of flows is always accompanied by their reterritorialization on a body, a person, an image, a name” (Gilles Deleuze, *Anti-Oedipus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia* 316). Deleuze expounds upon this complex synthesis of the libidinal body and the Marxist desire of productivity in his seminar:

It's the same development, the same discovery, and the discovery is used in the same way—whether it's the revelation that wealth essentially belongs to a subject as general production, which is subsequently re-alienated as an activity in terms of private property, or whether it's the Freudian revelation that desire, as subjective activity, can only be understood as libido, beyond the objects and aims of desire, which is immediately re-alienated—not as a state of things but as an activity, using the coordinates of the family (*Anti-Oedipus I, Logic of Flows / 09*).

Deleuze and Guattari's analysis of the 'self', of the 'desiring machine' is structured and pivoted upon an 'Ego-loss'; the Freudian Oedipus bifurcates the desiring-machine into a herd, a herd that is reterritorialized with the axiomatic structures of capitalism's arbitrary and decoded flows – a condition that is only realized via a double entanglement of the Ego and the Self – as is witnessed in the theoretical 'double bind' of the neoliberal economy. The neoliberal economy and its 'double-bind' gyrate around the psychological streamlining and bifurcation of the decoded flow of desire amidst the productive machine. In a capitalist economy, the wealth of subjectivities is given up for the objective product – the wealth that comes into realisation via private property. The desiring-machine is hence repressed and oppressed on two fronts, both the psychological and the socioeconomic. The double bind of oppression is carried out by the agents of repression, which subsume libidinal desire and productive desire unto the paradigms of their decoded flows. The desiring-machine accordingly becomes a neurotic, for the first signs of a capitalist disjunction are 'depression': a condition that can be seen threaded through all the women in Rooney's book – stoic, unfeeling, doubly-alienated, and indifferently sad. Frances is plagued by the neurotic's desire to achieve salvation, the neoliberal depression of a capitalist economy suppressing her libidinal as well as productive desire, only to reallocate it within the concentric spheres of ideological circles, gives rise to her nihilistic suffering; for a

Freudian neurotic chases the security of the herd, it thrives on the bifurcations of the binaries governing the arbitrary and mathematically decoded flows of the economy. The neoliberal socioeconomic culture induces a neurosis, that can only be cured by ‘talking’, talking to a ‘therapist’, talking to a ‘friend’ – but the cure in itself is the bind – for the neurotic seeks refuge in his own mind, he seeks to absolve himself of the aberrations of neoliberal flows, to restore his libidinal desire and re-align it with the socioeconomic collective, the circles of concentric ideology. Miller remarks in *Sexus*, “the man who looks for security, even in the mind, is like a man who would chop off his limbs in order to have artificial ones which will give him no pain or trouble” (Miller 428). Frances’ inordinate and fluctuating desire to align herself with Nick, an exemplary symbol of the neurotic’s ‘hope of tranquillity’, if safety, and security is directly contrasted with her torrid and unstable affair with Bobby; the dynamics of their relationships is not postfeminist, unlike Jimenez’s suggestions, Frances’ Freudian neurotic seeks to mark a departure from the constant fluctuation amidst the ideological circles, and seeks its refuge in the illusory ‘security’ of Nick’s proposed alignment with the binaries of the capitalist desiring-machine. “I certainly never fantasised about a radiant future where I was paid to perform an economic role”, says Frances in her prescient third-person monologue – the lack of punctuation and conversational markers in Rooney’s writing indicates a deliberate graphological choice – a choice to deviate from the neurotic’s desire to be enclosed within preconfigured boundaries – “sometimes this felt like a failure to take an interest in my own life, which depressed me”, Frances continues as the symbolic desiring-machine who’s libidinal and productive flow of desire has been reterritorialized under the axioms of capitalist arbitrators; plagued with the neurotic’s ‘depression’ of not being able to participate in the concentric circles of ideology, she says, “on the other hand, I felt that my disinterest in wealth was ideologically healthy” (Rooney 23); Frances’ dilemma is the emblem of the neurosis a desiring-machine undergoes in a Deleuzian analysis – the neurotic being unable to identify with the binaries of capitalist flows

is afflicted with a nihilist depression, that he seeks to annihilate with the ‘talking cure’ of the therapist, who in turn imbues him with the eternal Oedipal ego of the family, the binaries of the father and the mother – hence, the crisscross of the oppressive bifurcations work and insidiously penetrate the socioeconomic and ontological conditions of life at an elemental level. Frances’ dynamics with Bobby and Nick are the prime example of her being unable reconcile herself with the flow of wealth, acquisition of private property, and the neurosis induced by the resulting subversion; the neurosis of her relationship with Bobby can only be counteracted with the ‘cure’ of adhering to the binary bifurcations of the capitalist desiring-machine with Nick.

The Body without Organs and Schizoanalysis:

The ‘cure’ provided by the psychoanalyst within the framework of decoded capitalist cash flows ultimately consolidates the neurotic’s catastrophic suffering; the ‘depression’ created within the desiring-machine can be misinterpreted by the analyst who acts as the agent of dispensing the ‘ego’. The analyst becomes a symbol of the Oedipal assertion upon the libidinal desire of the productive machine, as Miller unabashedly protests in his book:

Lie down, then, on the soft couch which the analyst provides ... the analyst has endless time and patience; every minute you detain him means money in his pocket ... whether you whine, howl, beg, weep, cajole, pray, or curse – he listens. He is just a big ear minus a sympathetic nervous system. He is impervious to everything but the truth. If you think it pays to fool him, then fool him. Who will be the loser? If you think he can help you, and not yourself, then stick to him until you rot (Miller 429-30).

Miller’s harsh invectives about the cultural practices of psychoanalysis have been duly incorporated by Deleuze and Guattari within the bedrock of their theoretical framework. The neurosis caused by psychological splits induced by the Oedipal structure of the Ego cannot

serve as its remedy – the weapon causing the wound cannot act as the victim’s saviour. The Oedipal family dynamic, involving the father and mother, creates a patrilineal system of signification—a libidinal flow based on gendered binaries. This system constructs individuals into distinct ideological subjects with a dominant Ego that operates on the pleasure principle. The Oedipal Ego transforms the desiring-machine subjects into an undifferentiated herd, dismantling outward subjectivities and reassigning them to successive positionalities within concentric ideological circles. It creates a ‘defining’ moment in the ontology of the subject, fostering a complacency rooted in repression. The unconscious becomes a fluid matrix of signifiers governed by external and objective preconscious memories. The neurotic state is stretched across multiple forces, which oppose and influence each other within the body of the desiring-machine. In Deleuze and Guattari’s analysis, repressing the free flow of desire in neurotics and deliberately extinguishing subversive psychosis fosters distrust in the capitalist machinery of financial and psychotherapeutic decoding. “This is the realm of the silent majority. And it is into these back rooms, behind the closed doors of the analyst’s office, in the wings of the Oedipal theatre, that Deleuze and Guattari weave their way” (Seem xvll). These back rooms smell of decay and serve as spaces of repressive containment for neurotics, left bewildered by the repression of desire’s flow within a bilateral capitalist structure. The book **Anti-Oedipus** is not merely a critique of ego-loss but also vehemently opposes traditional psychoanalytic methods. For Deleuze and Guattari, the neurotic’s problems can only be addressed through a counterfactual psychosis. The psychotic—or ‘schizo’—does not conform to ideological binaries; it bursts free from the spheres of capital flows, social and political realms, and extends to the world and history. The schizo is uncontained, and the resulting flow of desire reconnects the subject to the libidinal stream, moving away from binaries of wealth and private property. Deleuze not only problematises the failure of synthesising Marxist and Freudian ideas but also diagnoses the root of their integration issues. The neurotic is

characterised by an inability to merge with the repressed desiring-machines of the silent majority; his depression is seen as an abnormality to be cured. Deleuze criticises the Freudian ‘talking cure,’ arguing it reintroduces binaries within the socio-economic flux of desire. He advocates that psychoanalysis should be replaced by ‘schizoanalysis’ as a revolutionary healing method for the ideological subject. Mark Seem’s introduction to *Anti-Oedipus* offers an expert overview of schizoanalysis.

What it attempts to cure us of is the cure itself ... [psychoanalysis] measures everything against neurosis and castration, schizoanalysis begins with the schizo, his breakdowns and his breakthroughs ... against the Oedipalized territorialities (Family, Church, School, Nation, Party), and especially the territoriality of the individual, *Anti-Oedipus* seeks to discover the “deterritorialized” flows of desire, the flows that have not been reduced to the Oedipal codes and the neuroticized territorialities, the desiring-machines that escape such codes as *lines of escape* leading elsewhere (Seem xvll).

The watchwords of schizoanalysis duly move away from the precepts of oedipal binaries; it hinges upon a ‘code of delirium’. The schizo moves through the channels and codes of ideology in a delirious disregard for semantic boundaries; the psychosis induced upon a schizo makes him a fluid receptor of desires that have otherwise remained repressed or oedipalised. The fluidity of delirium accords the schizo an induced and inveterate repulsion to any and every format of an axiom, the schizo deliberately scrambles, breaks free, and conflates disparate codes altogether – regardless of their genealogy – the schizo constantly and perpetually works against the grain of laws, codes, binaries, and the circumventing ideological circles. The schizo passes through the circles of the social to the World/Historical and back again to the political and personal with an absolute irreverance for reterritorialized codes and obstructions to the flows of innate desires – both libidinal and productive. Deleuze and Guattari have directly

picked up the idea of the schizo breaking all boundaries and moving beyond ideologies from Antonin Artaud's 'apocalyptic vision'. Artaud was himself plagued by the visions of 'the void' and a 'keen nothingness' circumnavigating the ontological genealogy of the Earth. Artaud deliberately moved away from the idea of a transcendental signifier, a God, embodying the emblem of all meanings, and established a disordered fluctuation of desires. For Artaud, merely the truth of nothingness, the void, an apocalypse of spells and demons that governed the lack of any quantifiable episteme plaguing the topography of the Earth persisted within it. The free state of nature, the lack of a transcendental God, and the irreverence to all formal codes dictate the psychotic mania induced in Deleuze and Guattari's schizoanalysis – "Artaud's apocalypse was a culmination of his lifelong fight against the Law, the Law of language, of cinema, of theatre, of progenitors, of family, of surrealism, of the body and, of the mind" (Finbow). For Deleuze, Guattari and Artaud, psychiatry becomes a mode of superimposition of varying degrees of 'mania of persecution'; the psychiatrist himself serves the agency of a law that has been arbitrarily imposed by a self-made transcendental lawmaker. The absence of axioms, the deliberate breakaway from the binaries of 'the father', 'the mother', and 'the child', accords for a true cure from the shackles of the concentric circles of ideology levied onto its desiring-machines and other various recipients, diachronically.

Drawing on Daniel Schreber's account of his confrontation with the schizophrenic illness of the mind, Deleuze and Guattari not only diagnose the problem with the constant coding, encoding, and decoding of the desiring-machine and its natural flows and fluctuations, but also provide a imminent solution to break apart and annihilate from the structural hierarchies of the capitalist machine and the fatalities of the neurosis it induces in the binary realms of oedipal bifurcations. Schreber's account of his experience as a schizo depicts numerous constructions of spells, minor gods, major worlds, and a plethora of unconventionally arcane knowledge systems. His curious account of 'being devoid of a

stomach’ and a ‘stomach miraculously appearing’ within him every time he sought to eat brought an epiphany to Deleuze and Guattari’s analysis. The innate and ingrained lack of stomach in a schizophrenic’s anatomy made Deleuze and Guattari contemplate and theorize about the innate lack of meaning, a body devoid of a stomach – a body devoid of organs. The ‘Body without Organs’ evolved as the innate and primordial condition of existence, engulfed with an ideological schizophrenia, the Body without Organs is a site of flow and flux, smooth and transparent, a fallow field devoid of the extrinsic plantations of the ‘organs of meaning and structure’. The Body without Organs is “the consciousness of nothing, upon which all consciousness of something enriches itself, takes on meaning and shape” (Derrida 8). The Body without Organs is purely an affective concept, devoid of palpable anatomy. Deleuze and Guattari famously enumerated the phenomenon of the Body without Organs as “not an empty body stripped of organs, but a body upon which that which serves as organs (functions, flows, etc.) is distributed according to crowd phenomena, in Brownian motion, in the form of atoms of the body” (Gilles Deleuze, *Anti Oedipus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia* 30), the Body without Organs is a form of resisting desiring-machine, stripped to its bare essentials, an innate and primal concept. The only way the decoded and reterritorialized flows of capitalism and desire can be recalibrated into a system devoid of hierarchies, binaries, and oppression is vis-à-vis the sociological inception of an ideological schizophrenia – a complete and utter disregard for the laws, rules, and conventional taxonomies of the Oedipal as well as capital flows. “The BwO is opposed not to the organs but to that organization of the organs called the organism” (Gilles Deleuze, *A Thousand Plateaus* 158), this is integral to the theoretical outset of the Body without Organs, Deleuze and Guattari do not suggest a complete annihilation of our organs but vehemently oppose their systematic and structural redistribution upon the Brownian motion of the primordial desiring-Body. This is what gives rise to the notion of a ‘rhizomatic unconsciousness’, that is the unconscious is not plagued by the obscure and obfuscated

significations of Freudian psychoanalytic onslaught, but has fissures and roots that germinate in all directions – convulsing, interlocking, and crisscrossing amidst their roots – but never taking a definite shape, size, or form. The Body without Organs and the schizoanalysis aim “to break the holds of power and institute research into a new collective subjectivity and a revolutionary healing of mankind. For we are sick, of ourselves!” (Seem xxi).

Neurotic Subjectivities of Rooney’s Characters:

Sally Rooney’s book, *Conversations with Friends*, is the quintessential exemplar of a protagonist being plagued by the neurotic depressive episodes of having to persist within the acculturation of a neoliberal, postfeminist desiring-machine. Frances’ inherent desires, which are constantly in flux, form an arbitrarily defined Brownian motion as an offshoot of their primordial meaninglessness; they have been forcefully streamlined and dictated to exist within the ontological uncertainty and hierarchical panopticons of power and preordained laws of subjugation. The neurosis, depressive, and nihilistic aloofness she experiences as an ideological Subject of a socioeconomic setup that thrives on dismantling subjectivities and gyrates upon the objective wealth accumulation in the form of private property, sustained by the genealogies of kinship and patrilineal filial setups, that dictate the capitalist economy (binding the desiring-machine) into the binaries of a monogamous, cis-gendered heterosexual order of romantic and affective governance, can only be resolved when she finds her ‘forbidden’ solace in Nick, an older married man, who becomes her existential subversion to the monogamous heterosexual economy of capital and wealth accumulation. Her open-ended, unresolved, and essentially hierarchically subversive relationship with Nick is definitive of the desiring-machine returning to its initial primordial condition of the ‘Body without structural Organs’. In one of her internal monologues, Frances muses about how she felt like she was:

Like an empty cup, which Nick had emptied out, and now I had to look at what had spilled out of me: all my delusional believes about my own value and my pretensions of being a kind of person I wasn't. While I was full of these things I couldn't see them. Now that I was nothing, only an empty glass I could see everything about myself (Rooney 287).

Frances' internal monologue about being able to witness the entirety of her persona's breadth only after she was devoid of every affectation and superimposed belief about herself is highly suggestive of Deleuze and Guattari's explication of the Body without Organs: a site which is only realized post the Subject's Ego-loss, as the ideological subject plods out of the hierarchies and binaries of the oedipal structures and streamlined modes of desires, beyond the axiomatic outlooks of the socioeconomic tapestry of his vicinity, he transcends beyond the realms of the World/Historical – a constant storehouse of the diachronically evolving desiring-machines – the summit of the World/Historical is devoid of a God, a prescient and omniscient entity that attributes meaning, instead it is a fluctuating field, evened out by its own frictionless existence. “Jesus always wanted to be the better person, and so did I” (Rooney 205), Frances asserts after spending an inordinate amount of time perusing through the Gospels and the New Testament, an atypical assertion of a schizo, the passive denunciation and the blasphemous equalisation of the Self with the Divine is a characteristic of the delirium induced by the desiring-Body left unstructured and smooth sans the presence of organs on it. “The world was like a crumpled ball of newspaper to me, something to kick around” (Rooney 221): Frances muses as a quintessentially displaced schizo, with her keen disregard for the world and its structures proper, her defiance for the heterosexual conventionalities, and its assorted monogamous precepts, Frances marks a stark departure from the inclinations and intrinsically decoded desires to establish a genealogical kinship, or a patrilineal filial connection that would ensure the preservation of her axiomatic assets, i.e. wealth in the form of private property – being

passed down to generations vis a vis the modes and binary conventions of the oedipal family. Frances exercises her will as a delirious non-member of the silent majority that has been taught to internalise its own repression, as assessed by Deleuze and Guattari. Frances' subversion of the rungs of the ladder of conventionalities depicts a schizo 'subject-group', in stark contrast with a neurotic 'subjugated group', who is:

A group whose libidinal investments are themselves revolutionary, it causes desire to penetrate into the social field, and subordinates the socius or the forms of power to desiring-production; productive of desire and a desire that produces, the subject-group always ... opposes ... a group superego (Seem xxi-xxii).

Frances constantly disengages herself from the transversality and coefficients of a 'group superego', i.e. she moves away from the Freudian concepts of a transcendental and axiomatic morality that dictates and guides the actions of the silent and repressed majority. In a World/Historical devoid of externally imposed meanings, primarily governed by the subversion of the Body without Organs, the theology of morality becomes as outdated and as oppressive as the outright penal codes of power and discipline. Morality and Law become the synonymous vanguards of a dictatorial regime, since non-adherence with the law of the land makes it a trespass in the eyes of the capitalist-state, which can issue disciplinarian punitive actions under the garb of reestablishing and protecting the codes of morality, conduct, and kinship; for Frances to envision the world as crumpled newspaper speaks volumes, both literally and figuratively, the axioms dictating what constitutes as 'news' and what is to be printed for public circulation become as redundant as the meanings superimposed upon the naturally primordial state of the Body without Organs. The loss of these imbued morality codes can only be applied via a collective Ego-loss of the conflated subjugated group of desiring-machines. "People grow defensive and panic at the idea of experiencing ego-loss through the use of drugs or collective experiences" (Seem xxii), since the experience of delirium is a

forbidden luxury in the realms of ideologically concentrated circles. The neurotic seeks to escape the untethered transcendence of a collective ego-loss since he has been oedipally conditioned to adhere to the binary modes of heterosexual kinship. In seeking the perfidious solace of a collective amalgamation, the ideologically entrenched subject fatally loses his sense of agency and subjectivity to the external objectivities. In its essence:

Deleuze and Guattari's schizoanalytic approach serves ... a healing process. Its major task is to destroy the oedipalized and neuroticized individual dependencies through the forging of a collective subjectivity, a nonfascist subject—anti-Oedipus. Anti-Oedipus is an individual or a group that no longer functions in terms of beliefs and that comes to redeem mankind (Seem xxii-xxiii).

This healing process of reverting to one's primordial state, a state of being a body unpopulated by its axiomatic codes, territorialities, and organs, as devised by Deleuze and Guattari ensures the inception and outset of an actual process of amelioration for the ideological subject, as is proposed in *Anti-Oedipus*, the Freudian 'cure' of the analyst's couch merely seeks to ascertain the codes and axioms unnaturally levied onto the unrestrained, uncontained, and universally subjective desiring-Body. In their assessments of ideological amelioration, Deleuze and Guattari acclaim the revolutionaries and the people who can palpably assert themselves as subjective entities; they uphold their psychotic deliriums of death, stoicism, and a general disregard for the axioms of the concurrently facile 'zones of ideology'. Frances embodies the outlook of a subversive revolutionary, a seer, a subjective desiring-body that aims to break free from the limiting significations of monogamy, from the labels, bifurcations, and everlasting principles of kinship laid down in front of her by the oedipal binaries of the family. In her pursuit of Nick and forging an affective, all-consuming relationship with him, Frances defies and transmutes past the myriad conventions of her sociocultural milieu: age, monogamy,

adultery, physical consumption, and emotional apathy towards the binaries of labels of identity, her general disregard for all forms of binaries and significations besides her primordial pull of desire towards Nick, makes her a compelling study under the paradigms of Deleuze and Guattari's theoretical assessment. Their relationship in its atypical quintessence of defiance and subversion never reaches a *dénouement*; even as Rooney ends her narrativity, she leaves the chain of signifiers and the fate of Nick and Frances' relationship open-ended, as Frances describes during the concluding lines of *Conversations with Friends*:

I closed my eyes. Things and people moved around me, taking positions in obscure hierarchies, participating in systems I didn't know about and never would. A complex network of objects and concepts. You live through certain things before you understand them. You can't always take the analytical position (Rooney 321).

Rooney's narrative, ergo, depicts the neurotic disjunction of Frances' subjectivity expertly, as she weaves her tale around a state of 'constantly becoming'.

Conclusion:

The concluding excerpts from the book situate Frances as the quintessential 'schizo' of Deleuze and Guattari's *Anti-Oedipus*, jostling and segregating her pathway from the convoluted ideological networks and axioms of binary conventionalities; she emerges as a transcendental desiring-Body who has undergone the amelioration of an Ego-loss. Frances' paucity of neurotic efforts to control and dictate how the dictums of her life play out: socially, romantically, culturally, filially, and platonically, enables her to readily move beyond the concentrated zones of 'false consciousnesses' pervading and parading themselves as agents of touchstone significations. Sally Rooney's Frances is not a contentious portrait of neoliberal or postfeminist ideations; instead, Frances strikingly absolves herself of the internalisation of

every repressive hierarchy and ideologically convoluted axioms of morality, law, justice, discipline, power, and private property: which ultimately sets her free, as a healed, subjective desiring-body, that does not adhere to the inherently meaningless axioms of the capitalist-machinery.

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